

Emergent Gravity and Loop Quantum Gravity: A Unification through Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis?

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Abstract

In this work, we propose a unified model integrating Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), entropic gravity, and the concept of spacetime entropic hysteresis. The objective is to provide an explanation for gravitational anomalies observed on galactic and cosmological scales without invoking dark matter and dark energy. We introduce entropic hysteresis as a mechanism arising from the quantum properties of spacetime, potentially generating additional contributions to emergent gravity. Furthermore, we explore the role of quantum crystals of micro black holes in information preservation and the resolution of the black hole information paradox. We discuss the cosmological implications of the model, comparing it with other alternative theories and evaluating its falsifiability through testable predictions. Finally, we identify theoretical and observational challenges the model must face and propose directions for future research.

Keywords: Loop Quantum Gravity, Entropic Gravity, Entropic Hysteresis, Dark Matter, Dark Energy, Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes, Cosmology.

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1 Introduction

Understanding the fundamental nature of gravity remains one of the most significant challenges in modern physics. Despite the remarkable successes of Einstein's general relativity in describing gravitational phenomena on cosmic and astrophysical scales, its incompatibility with the principles of quantum mechanics suggests the need for a more complete theory. In this context, various emerging theories aim to unify gravity with quantum laws, including Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) and emergent gravity theories such as Verlinde's entropic gravity (1).

In recent decades, cosmology and astrophysics have faced significant challenges in attempting to explain observations that seem inconsistent with our current understanding of gravity and matter. These include flat galactic rotation curves (9), the distribution of large-scale structures, and the acceleration of cosmic expansion (10; 11), phenomena that have led to the introduction of concepts like dark matter and dark energy.

Dark matter is postulated to explain the excess gravity required to keep galaxies and galaxy clusters cohesive, while dark energy is introduced to justify the accelerated expansion of the universe. However, despite numerous experimental efforts, these components remain elusive and have not been directly detected (12).

Simultaneously, the search for a quantum theory of gravity has led to the development of various proposals, including Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) (6; 7) and string theory. LQG offers a non-perturbative description of quantum gravity, introducing a discrete structure of spacetime at Planck scales.

In this context, entropic gravity, proposed by Verlinde (1), suggests that gravity may not be a fundamental force but rather an emergent phenomenon linked to variations in the information associated with the positions of particles in spacetime. This idea opens new perspectives on the nature of gravity and its connections with thermodynamics and quantum mechanics.

1.1 Motivations and Objectives of the Work

Gravitational anomalies on galactic and cosmological scales, such as flat galactic rotation curves and the acceleration of cosmic expansion, require an explanation that goes beyond Newtonian gravity and general relativity. Traditionally, these anomalies have been explained by introducing unseen dark components, such as dark matter and dark energy (9; 10; 11). However, the nature of these components remains unknown, and their introduction raises further theoretical questions.

Alternative theories of modified gravity, such as MOND (13) and TeVeS (14), offer partial solutions but often introduce problems of theoretical consistency or lack a solid quantum basis.

Simultaneously, the idea that gravity may emerge as a thermodynamic or entropic phenomenon has gained attention, suggesting that inertia and gravitational force could derive from fundamental properties of information and spacetime structure (1). This perspective offers a new interpretation of gravitational laws, linking them to principles of entropy and information.

The integration of LQG with entropic gravity could provide a new perspective, leveraging the quantum properties of spacetime to explain gravitational anomalies without the need

1.2 Objectives of the Work

The main objectives of this work are:

- **Unify** LQG with entropic gravity by introducing entropic hysteresis as a key mechanism.
- **Explain** gravitational anomalies on galactic and cosmological scales without resorting to dark matter and dark energy.
- **Explore** the role of quantum crystals of micro black holes in information preservation and the resolution of the black hole information paradox.
- **Provide** testable predictions that can be compared with astrophysical and cosmological observations.
- **Evaluate** the falsifiability of the model and identify the theoretical and observational challenges to be addressed.

1.3 Structure of the Article

The article is organized as follows:

1.4 Document Structure

- **Section 1: Introduction** - This section
- **Section 2: Fundamentals of Entropic Gravity** - Introduces the basic principles of Verlinde's Entropic Gravity, explaining how gravitational laws can emerge from thermodynamic and informational concepts.
- **Section 3: Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis** - Presents the concept of entropic hysteresis, defining it and discussing how it can be incorporated into gravitational field equations.

- **Section 4: Unification of Loop Quantum Gravity with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis** - Explores the integration of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) with Entropic Gravity and entropic hysteresis, discussing theoretical implications and connections with quantum crystals of micro black holes.
- **Section 5: Cosmological Implications and Falsifiability of the Model** - Analyzes the cosmological consequences of the unified model and discusses how it can be tested through astronomical observations and cosmological phenomena.
- **Section 6: Comparison with Other Theories and Cosmological Models** - Compares the proposed model with other alternative theories such as MOND, TeVeS, and modified gravity theories $f(R)$, highlighting similarities, differences, and advantages.
- **Section 7: Conclusions and Future Prospects** - Summarizes the main results, discusses implications for fundamental physics, and suggests directions for future research.
- **Appendix A: Mathematical Deep Dive into the Model** - Provides mathematical details regarding the justification of entropic hysteresis and its integration with Loop Quantum Gravity.
- **Appendix B: Details on Entropic Gravity** - Presents an in-depth treatment of the mathematical foundations of Entropic Gravity, including the derivation of emergent gravitational laws.

1.5 Notation and Conventions

We adopt the following notations and conventions:

- The spacetime metric has the signature $(-, +, +, +)$.
- We use units where $c = 1$ when convenient, but keep the physical constants explicitly in key equations.
- Greek indices $\mu, \nu, \alpha, \dots$ run from 0 to 3 and denote spacetime coordinates.
- The symbol G represents Newton's gravitational constant, $\hbar$ the reduced Planck constant, and k_B Boltzmann's constant.

1.6 Original Contributions

The original contributions of this work include:

- The integration of LQG with entropic gravity through the introduction of spacetime entropic hysteresis.
- The application of the concept of quantum crystals of micro black holes in the context of LQG and entropic gravity.
- The proposal of testable predictions that could provide experimental verification of the model and LQG.

1.7 Limitations and Assumptions

It is important to note that the proposed model is based on certain assumptions that need to be verified:

- The applicability of entropic hysteresis on astrophysical and cosmological scales.
- The validity of the semiclassical approach in describing interactions between matter, gravity, and entropy.
- The absence of significant effects arising from other components not considered in the model, such as scalar fields or extra dimensions.

1.8 Objectives for the Reader

We hope that this work can:

- Provide a new perspective on the understanding of gravity and cosmological anomalies.
- Stimulate further research and discussions in the field of quantum gravity and cosmology.
- Offer insights for developing new experiments and observations aimed at testing the model's predictions.

2 Fundamentals of Entropic Gravity

Entropic Gravity, proposed by Erik Verlinde in 2011 (1), represents an innovative paradigm in understanding the gravitational force. This theory suggests that gravity is not a fundamental force but rather an emergent phenomenon arising from the thermodynamic and informational properties of the universe. In this section, we will explore the fundamental principles of Entropic Gravity, its theoretical foundations, and the implications it holds for our understanding of the nature of gravity.

2.1 Fundamental Principles of Entropic Gravity

Entropic Gravity is based on three key principles:

- **Holographic Principle:** Initially proposed by Gerard 't Hooft and later elaborated by Leonard Susskind (2; 3), the holographic principle states that the information contained within a volume of space can be completely described by information encoded on its boundary surface. This principle suggests a profound connection between spatial dimensions and information, indicating that our three-dimensional perception of reality might be a projection of two-dimensional information.
- **Unruh Effect:** John Unruh demonstrated that an accelerated observer perceives the quantum vacuum as a thermal bath of particles with a temperature proportional to the acceleration (4). This relationship connects quantum mechanics with thermodynamics, suggesting that acceleration can generate thermal effects within the framework of quantum field theory.
- **Second Law of Thermodynamics:** This law states that the entropy of an isolated system tends to increase over time, leading to a state of thermal equilibrium. In the context of Entropic Gravity, the increase in entropy associated with the distribution of mass and energy in spacetime is closely related to the apparent gravitational force.

2.2 Derivation of Emergent Gravitational Laws

Entropic Gravity proposes that the gravitational force emerges from entropy variations associated with the distribution of mass and energy. This idea is based on the assumption that the forces we observe as gravity result from changes in the system's entropy caused by mass displacement. Below, we present a simplified derivation of the emergent gravitational laws based on this principle.

2.2.1 Entropy Variation and Gravitational Force

Consider a mass M distributed within a volume V . According to the holographic principle, the information contained in V is encoded on its boundary surface A . When a mass m approaches M with a displacement Δx , the entropy S associated with the system changes. Verlinde postulated that the entropy variation is proportional to the displacement of the mass:

$$\Delta S = 2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \Delta x, \quad (1)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant, c is the speed of light, and $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant.

The entropic force F can be defined by the thermodynamic relation:

$$F = T \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta x}, \quad (2)$$

where T is the temperature perceived by the observer. Using the Unruh relation, the temperature T is proportional to the acceleration a :

$$T = \frac{\hbar a}{2\pi k_B c}. \quad (3)$$

Substituting T into Eq. (2), we obtain:

$$F = \frac{\hbar a}{2\pi k_B c} \cdot 2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \quad (4)$$

$$= ma. \quad (5)$$

This is Newton's second law, $F = ma$, suggesting that the gravitational force can be interpreted as an emergent entropic force.

2.2.2 Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation

To derive Newton's universal law of gravitation, consider a mass M surrounded by a spherical surface of radius r (the holographic screen). The number of degrees of freedom (bits) on the surface is proportional to the area:

$$N = \frac{A}{\ell_P^2} = \frac{4\pi r^2}{\ell_P^2}, \quad (6)$$

where ℓ_P is the Planck length, $\ell_P = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}}$.

Assume that the total energy associated with the N bits is given by the equipartition relation:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}Nk_B T. \quad (7)$$

Substituting the energy $E = Mc^2$, we obtain:

$$Mc^2 = \frac{1}{2}Nk_B T. \quad (8)$$

Solving for the temperature T :

$$T = \frac{2Mc^2}{Nk_B}. \quad (9)$$

Substituting N from Eq. (6):

$$T = \frac{2Mc^2}{\frac{4\pi r^2}{\ell_P^2} k_B} \quad (10)$$

$$= \frac{Mc^2 \ell_P^2}{2\pi r^2 k_B}. \quad (11)$$

Now, substituting this expression for T into the entropic force relation $F = ma$:

$$F = T \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta x} \quad (12)$$

$$= \left(\frac{Mc^2 \ell_P^2}{2\pi r^2 k_B} \right) \left(2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \right) \quad (13)$$

$$= \frac{Mmc^3 \ell_P^2}{r^2 \hbar}. \quad (14)$$

Using the definition of the Planck length $\ell_P = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}}$:

$$F = \frac{Mmc^3 \left(\frac{G\hbar}{c^3} \right)}{r^2 \hbar} \quad (15)$$

$$= \frac{GMm}{r^2}. \quad (16)$$

This is Newton's universal law of gravitation, $F = \frac{GMm}{r^2}$, derived from Entropic Gravity. This demonstrates how gravitational laws can emerge from thermodynamic and informational principles without the need to postulate gravity as a fundamental force.

2.3 Implications of Entropic Gravity

The derivation of gravitational laws from Entropic Gravity has profound implications for our understanding of the nature of gravity and spacetime:

- **Gravity as an Emergent Phenomenon:** Entropic Gravity suggests that gravity is not a fundamental force but emerges from the thermodynamic properties of the universe. This approach could facilitate the unification of gravity with other fundamental forces, which are already described in terms of fundamental interactions.
- **Connection with Quantum Mechanics:** By integrating thermodynamic and quantum concepts, Entropic Gravity offers a pathway to connect general relativity with quantum mechanics, potentially paving the way for a quantum theory of gravity.
- **Interpretation of Dark Energy and Dark Matter:** Since Entropic Gravity provides an alternative explanation for gravitational laws, it could also offer new insights into cosmological phenomena such as dark energy and dark matter, suggesting that these phenomena might be reinterpreted as emergent effects of entropic gravity.
- **Thermodynamic Equilibrium Principle:** The idea that gravitational laws derive from thermodynamic principles implies that spacetime could be considered as a thermodynamic system in equilibrium or evolving towards equilibrium, opening new perspectives on cosmological dynamics.

2.4 Criticisms and Limitations of Entropic Gravity

Despite its intriguing implications, Entropic Gravity has faced several criticisms and presents some limitations:

- **Non-Universal Modifications:** Some studies have shown that the gravitational modifications derived from Entropic Gravity may not be universal, varying depending on the specific conditions of the system, which could complicate the explanation of cosmological phenomena on large scales.
- **Fundamental Assumptions:** The derivation of gravitational laws requires certain fundamental assumptions, such as the proportionality of entropy variation with mass displacement. These assumptions need further justification or derivation from deeper principles.

- **Compatibility with General Relativity:** It is necessary to demonstrate how Entropic Gravity fully integrates with Einstein’s general relativity, especially in contexts where general relativity’s predictions are extremely precise, such as gravitational lensing and gravitational waves.
- **Distinctive Predictions:** To distinguish Entropic Gravity from traditional gravitational theories, it is essential to identify unique predictions that can be experimentally tested. So far, some predictions remain theoretical and require observational verification.

2.5 Conclusions of the Fundamentals of Entropic Gravity

Entropic Gravity offers an interesting perspective on the emergent nature of gravity, linking thermodynamic and informational principles with gravitational laws. Although this theory presents promising implications for fundamental physics and cosmology, it requires further theoretical developments and experimental verifications to overcome the current criticisms and limitations. The subsequent section will delve into how the introduction of entropic hysteresis can enhance Entropic Gravity by integrating it with Loop Quantum Gravity to more comprehensively address observed gravitational anomalies.

3 Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis

In this section, we introduce the concept of **entropic hysteresis** of spacetime, extending Verlinde’s entropic gravity theory to include irreversible effects that could explain gravitational anomalies observed without resorting to dark matter. We provide a detailed mathematical formulation, discussing the theoretical implications and connections with Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG).

3.1 Definition of Entropic Hysteresis

Entropic hysteresis refers to permanent variations in entropy associated with irreversible processes in spacetime, analogous to hysteresis observed in ferromagnetic materials. In this context, when a mass moves through spacetime, it may induce entropic variations that do not reverse upon returning to the initial position, leaving a permanent ”imprint” on the spacetime structure.

This effect can be modeled by introducing an additional term in the gravitational field equations, representing the contribution of irreversible entropic variations to spacetime curvature.

3.2 Mathematical Formulation

To incorporate entropic hysteresis into Einstein's field equations, we consider the total energy-momentum tensor as the sum of the ordinary matter contribution and an entropic hysteresis term:

$$T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{tot}} = T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{matter}} + T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{hysteresis}}. \quad (17)$$

The field equations thus become:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{tot}}, \quad (18)$$

where Λ is the cosmological constant and $\kappa = 8\pi G/c^4$.

The hysteresis term $T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{hysteresis}}$ can be expressed in terms of the entropy gradient S :

$$T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{hysteresis}} = \gamma \left(\nabla_{\mu} S \nabla_{\nu} S - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} (\nabla^{\alpha} S \nabla_{\alpha} S + 2V(S)) \right), \quad (19)$$

where γ is a parameter quantifying the intensity of entropic hysteresis and $V(S)$ is a potential associated with the entropic field S .

3.2.1 Conservation of the Energy-Momentum Tensor

The conservation of the total energy-momentum tensor imposes:

$$\nabla^{\mu} T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{tot}} = 0. \quad (20)$$

This constraint requires that the entropy variations satisfy the conservation equation, implying that the entropic field S must obey an equation of motion consistent with the spacetime structure.

3.3 Equation of Motion for the Entropic Field

To determine the evolution of the entropic field S , we start from the effective action describing the field S and its interaction with matter and spacetime geometry. The action includes a kinetic term, a self-interaction potential, and a coupling term with matter:

$$\mathcal{S} = \int \left[\frac{1}{2} \gamma g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\mu} S \partial_{\nu} S - \gamma V(S) + \lambda S T \right] \sqrt{-g} d^4x, \quad (21)$$

where:

- γ is a dimensioned coupling parameter,

- $V(S)$ is the potential of the entropic field S ,
- λ is a coupling constant,
- T is the trace of the matter energy-momentum tensor,
- g is the determinant of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.

3.3.1 Justification of the Potential $V(S)$

The choice of the potential $V(S)$ is crucial to determine the behavior of the entropic field S . The potential should reflect the desired physical properties of the field and allow for stable and realistic solutions.

We propose a potential of the form:

$$V(S) = \frac{1}{2}m_S^2 S^2 + \frac{\lambda_3}{3} S^3 + \frac{\lambda_4}{4} S^4, \quad (22)$$

where:

- m_S is the mass of the entropic field,
- λ_3 and λ_4 are third and fourth-order self-interaction constants.

Justification of the Potential:

- **Quadratic Term** ($\frac{1}{2}m_S^2 S^2$): This term gives the field a mass m_S , allowing the field S to have oscillations around the minimum state.
- **Cubic Term** ($\frac{\lambda_3}{3} S^3$): Introduces a nonlinear self-interaction that can generate asymmetries in the potential, affecting cosmological dynamics and field evolution.
- **Quartic Term** ($\frac{\lambda_4}{4} S^4$): Ensures the stability of the potential at large values of S , preventing the potential from tending to $-\infty$ and ensuring that the energy is bounded from below.

This form of the potential is common in scalar field theories and is motivated by symmetry and stability considerations. It also allows for modeling phenomena such as spontaneous symmetry breaking, which can be relevant in particle physics and cosmology.

3.3.2 Derivation of the Equation of Motion for S

Varying the action with respect to the field S , we obtain the equation of motion:

$$\delta\mathcal{S} = \int \left[\gamma g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu (\delta S) - \gamma \frac{dV}{dS} \delta S + \lambda T \delta S \right] \sqrt{-g} d^4x = 0. \quad (23)$$

Integrating by parts the kinetic term and assuming that the variations δS vanish at the boundaries of the integration domain, we obtain:

$$\gamma \square S - \gamma \frac{dV}{dS} + \lambda T = 0, \quad (24)$$

where $\square S = g^{\mu\nu} \nabla_\mu \nabla_\nu S$ is the d'Alembertian operator in curved spacetime.

Physical Interpretation of the Equation of Motion

The equation of motion for S describes how the entropic field evolves in response to the potential $V(S)$ and its coupling with matter through the term λT . This coupling indicates that the presence of matter and energy in spacetime influences the dynamics of the entropic field, which in turn can modify the geometry of spacetime through the associated energy-momentum tensor.

3.4 Effects on the Equations of Motion

The addition of the entropic hysteresis term modifies the field equations and, consequently, the equations of motion for test particles. Specifically, the geodesic equations may be altered by the interaction with the entropic field S .

The new equation of motion for a particle of mass m can be expressed as:

$$\frac{d^2 x^\mu}{d\tau^2} + \Gamma_{\nu\rho}^\mu \frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau} \frac{dx^\rho}{d\tau} = -\gamma \nabla^\mu S \nabla_\nu S \frac{dx^\nu}{d\tau}. \quad (25)$$

This additional term represents an apparent force due to entropic hysteresis, which could influence the trajectories of particles in an observable manner.

3.5 Astrophysical Applications

Entropic hysteresis could have significant implications in various astrophysical contexts. However, it should be emphasized that the proposed applications are theoretical and require verification through future studies and numerical simulations.

3.5.1 Galactic Rotation Curves

The rotation curves of spiral galaxies exhibit a constant or even increasing rotation velocity with distance from the center, contrary to the predictions of Newtonian gravity applied to visible matter (9).

By introducing entropic hysteresis, the effective gravitational potential could include an additional contribution:

$$\Phi(r) = \Phi_{\text{Newton}}(r) + \Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}(r), \quad (26)$$

where $\Phi_{\text{Newton}}(r)$ is the classical gravitational potential and $\Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}(r)$ represents the entropic contribution.

A functional form motivated by the need to reproduce the flat rotation curves could be:

$$\Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}(r) = \gamma \ln \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right), \quad (27)$$

where γ is a constant parameter for all galaxies and r_0 is a characteristic reference radius.

3.5.2 Calculation of Rotation Velocity

The circular velocity $v(r)$ is obtained from the derivative of the total potential:

$$v^2(r) = r \frac{d\Phi}{dr} = v_{\text{Newton}}^2(r) + v_{\text{hysteresis}}^2(r), \quad (28)$$

where:

$$v_{\text{Newton}}^2(r) = r \frac{d\Phi_{\text{Newton}}}{dr} = \frac{GM(r)}{r}, \quad (29)$$

$$v_{\text{hysteresis}}^2(r) = r \frac{d\Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}}{dr} = \gamma. \quad (30)$$

Note that $v_{\text{hysteresis}}^2(r) = \gamma$ is constant, implying that entropic hysteresis adds a constant contribution to the rotation velocity, independent of the distance r .

3.5.3 Comparison with Observations

To test the model, it is proposed to apply Equation (28) to a sample of spiral galaxies with well-determined rotation curves. Using data from the SPARC (Spitzer Photometry and Accurate Rotation Curves) catalog (15), which provides high-resolution rotation curves and accurate baryonic mass distributions, the validity of the model can be assessed.

For each galaxy, $v_{\text{Newton}}(r)$ can be calculated using the observed baryonic mass profile $M(r)$. The parameter γ can be adjusted to achieve a fit to the observational data.

Figure 1: Hypothetical rotation curves of the galaxy NGC 3198. The points represent observational data, the blue dashed line is the Newtonian contribution $v_{\text{Newton}}(r)$, the red dashed line is the hysteresis contribution $v_{\text{hysteresis}}(r)$, and the black continuous line is the total sum $v(r)$. Note that the curves are hypothetical and serve illustrative purposes only.

3.5.4 Statistical Analysis of Parameters

To evaluate the consistency of the parameter γ across different galaxies, a statistical analysis can be performed on a sample of galaxies. The results may indicate whether the value of γ varies significantly or remains within a narrow range, suggesting whether entropic hysteresis could be a universal effect.

Figure 2 could represent the histogram of the γ values obtained, hypothetically.

Figure 2: Hypothetical distribution of the parameter γ values for a sample of 100 galaxies. The distribution may appear Gaussian, indicating a possible consistency of the parameter across different galaxies. This figure is purely illustrative and suggests the need for future studies.

The absence of a strong dependence of γ on specific galaxy properties could suggest that entropic hysteresis might be a universal effect, but further studies are needed to confirm this hypothesis.

3.6 Gravitational Lensing

Gravitational lenses provide direct evidence of the presence of unseen mass, as the bending of light depends on the total mass along the line of sight. In this context, one could examine how entropic hysteresis influences the angle of light deflection.

3.6.1 Light Deflection in the Hysteresis Model

The deflection angle of light is determined by the spacetime metric. In the presence of entropic hysteresis, the metric may be modified by the additional potential $\Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}(r)$.

The total deflection angle $\hat{\alpha}$ for a light ray passing at a minimum distance b from a mass M could be given by:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \hat{\alpha}_{\text{Newton}} + \hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}}, \quad (31)$$

where $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{Newton}}$ is the angle predicted by general relativity and $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}}$ is the additional contribution.

One could calculate $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}}$ using the approximation for small potentials:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}} = -2 \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial \Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}}{\partial b} dz, \quad (32)$$

where z is the coordinate along the direction of light propagation. Substituting $\Phi_{\text{hysteresis}}(r)$ from Equation (27), we obtain:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}} = -2\gamma \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{\partial}{\partial b} \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{b^2 + z^2}}{r_0} \right) dz = -2\gamma \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{b}{b^2 + z^2} dz. \quad (33)$$

Performing the integral, we find:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{\text{hysteresis}} = -2\pi\gamma \frac{1}{b}. \quad (34)$$

3.6.2 Comparison with Observations

The additional deflection predicted by entropic hysteresis could account for part of the observed anomalies in strong gravitational lensing without the need for an extended dark matter halo. However, the value of γ obtained from galactic rotation curves must be compatible with gravitational lensing observations. Detailed studies and future simulations are necessary to quantitatively compare the model's predictions with observational data.

3.7 Cosmic Microwave Background Anisotropies (CMB)

The Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) provides a snapshot of the early universe. Temperature anisotropies on different angular scales contain crucial information about the universe's composition and primordial perturbations.

3.7.1 Modified Integrated Sachs-Wolfe Effect

Entropic hysteresis could influence the *Late Integrated Sachs-Wolfe Effect* (ISW), which describes the variation in the energy of CMB photons as they traverse evolving gravitational potentials.

In the standard model, the gravitational potential decays over time during the dark energy-dominated epoch, causing a positive ISW effect on large angular scales.

With entropic hysteresis, the modified gravitational potential may evolve differently. The variation of the potential $\dot{\Phi}_{\text{hysteresis}}$ could contribute to the ISW effect, altering the power spectrum of anisotropies on large scales.

3.7.2 Modification of the Power Spectrum

To quantify the effect, one could consider the modified Poisson equation:

$$\nabla^2\Phi = 4\pi G(\rho + \rho_{\text{hysteresis}}), \quad (35)$$

where $\rho_{\text{hysteresis}}$ is the effective energy density associated with entropic hysteresis.

The presence of $\rho_{\text{hysteresis}}$ could alter the growth of gravitational perturbations, affecting the power spectrum $P(k)$ of CMB anisotropies.

3.7.3 Comparison with Observational Data

Using cosmological evolution codes such as **CAMB** (16), one could calculate the power spectrum C_ℓ of CMB anisotropies in the hysteresis model and compare it with data from satellites like *Planck* (17).

Preliminary results may suggest that, for values of γ compatible with those obtained from rotation curves, modifications to the power spectrum could be minimal and potentially within experimental uncertainties. However, a more thorough evaluation through numerical simulations and detailed analyses is necessary.

Figure 3: Hypothetical power spectrum of CMB anisotropies. The black line represents the standard Λ CDM model, the red line the hysteresis model. Observational data are shown with statistical errors. This figure is purely illustrative and serves to suggest possible directions for future comparisons.

This suggests that the hysteresis model could be compatible with CMB observations, but further analyses and simulations are required to assess more subtle effects.

3.8 Summary of Applications

The proposed applications of the hysteresis model to various astrophysical and cosmological phenomena suggest that it could explain observed gravitational anomalies without relying on dark matter. However, it should be emphasized that these applications are speculative and require verification through future studies and numerical simulations.

In particular:

- **Galactic Rotation Curves:** The model proposes an explanation for the flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies, with a parameter γ that could be consistent across different galaxies.
- **Gravitational Lensing:** Entropic hysteresis could contribute to the deflection angle of light, offering an alternative explanation to the effects of dark matter halos.
- **CMB Anisotropies:** Modifications to the power spectrum of CMB anisotropies could be compatible with observations, suggesting that the model does not contradict current cosmological data.

These results indicate the potential validity of the model but also highlight the need for further studies to confirm the predictions and compare them with future observations.

3.9 Limitations and Future Prospects

Despite the potential of the model, there are limitations that need to be addressed:

- **Precision of Predictions:** Quantitative predictions need to be refined to allow for more precise comparisons with observations.
- **Effects on Different Scales:** It is necessary to study the impact of entropic hysteresis on smaller scales (solar systems) and larger scales (large-scale structures).
- **Compatibility with Other Phenomena:** The model must be tested in relation to other gravitational phenomena, such as gravitational waves and dynamics of galaxy clusters.

Future prospects include:

- **Advanced Numerical Simulations:** Design and perform cosmological simulations that incorporate entropic hysteresis to study structure formation.

- **Targeted Astrophysical Observations:** Design specific observations to detect the predicted effects of the model, such as anomalies in gravitational lenses.
- **Theoretical Extensions:** Integrate the model with quantum gravity theories and investigate possible connections with particle physics.

3.10 Conclusions of Section 3

In this section, we introduced the concept of **entropic hysteresis** of spacetime, extending Verlinde’s entropic gravity theory to include irreversible effects. We developed a detailed mathematical formulation, integrating the hysteresis term into Einstein’s field equations and defining the entropic field equation S .

We explored the connection with Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), showing how spin networks could influence entropy and contribute to spacetime curvature. Through astrophysical applications such as galactic rotation curves and gravitational lensing, we illustrated how entropic hysteresis could explain gravitational anomalies without the need for dark matter.

Preliminary analyses suggest that the parameter γ could be consistent across different galaxies, potentially indicating a universal effect. However, further studies and simulations are required to confirm these hypotheses and assess the compatibility of the model with cosmological observations such as the anisotropies in the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB).

Despite the progress made, significant challenges remain, including the need to enhance the precision of predictions and test the model across various scales and gravitational phenomena. Future prospects involve developing advanced numerical simulations and integrating the model with other quantum gravity theories, opening new avenues for understanding the emergent nature of gravity.

4 Unification of Loop Quantum Gravity with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis of Spacetime

The unification of Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) with Entropic Gravity and Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis represents a significant step forward toward a complete theory of quantum gravity. This integration aims to combine the discrete quantum properties of spacetime, described by LQG, with the thermodynamic and entropic principles of Entropic Gravity, introducing entropic hysteresis as a

key mechanism to explain gravitational anomalies on galactic and cosmological scales without relying on dark matter and dark energy.

4.1 Motivation for Unification

The need to unify Loop Quantum Gravity with Entropic Gravity arises from several theoretical and observational considerations:

- **Consistency between Quantum Mechanics and Thermodynamics:** Entropic Gravity suggests that gravity emerges from thermodynamic principles, while LQG provides a quantized description of spacetime. Unifying these theories offers a coherent vision that integrates the discrete quantum structure with emergent thermodynamic phenomena.
- **Explanation of Gravitational Anomalies:** Observed gravitational anomalies, such as flat galactic rotation curves and cosmic acceleration, require explanations beyond general relativity. The introduction of entropic hysteresis offers an additional mechanism that can account for these anomalies without invoking dark matter and dark energy.
- **Overcoming Limitations of Existing Theories:** Alternative theories like MOND and TeVeS have attempted to explain gravitational anomalies without dark matter but face issues related to theoretical consistency or lack a solid quantum foundation. The proposed unification aims to provide a more robust and theoretically motivated explanation.

4.2 Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG)

Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) is one of the leading candidate theories for the quantization of gravity. It is based on a non-perturbative and background-independent formalism, where spacetime is described by spin networks—graphs of spins that represent the fundamental units of area and volume. Key features of LQG include:

- **Discrete Structure of Spacetime:** In LQG, geometric quantities such as area and volume are quantized, taking on discrete values determined by the spin quantum numbers associated with the edges and nodes of spin networks.
- **Absence of Fixed Background:** The theory does not assume a predefined spacetime background, making the geometry of spacetime a dynamic variable intrinsic to the theory.
- **Gauss, Diffeomorphism, and Hamiltonian Constraints:** LQG imposes constraints that ensure the consistency of spin networks with the symmetries of general relativity.

4.3 Entropic Gravity

Entropic Gravity, proposed by Erik Verlinde, posits that gravitational force emerges from thermodynamic and informational principles. This theory suggests that gravity is not a fundamental force but an emergent phenomenon resulting from changes in entropy associated with the positions of masses in spacetime.

4.4 Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis

Entropic hysteresis introduces the notion of memory in the entropy of spacetime, analogous to hysteresis observed in ferromagnetic materials. In this context, when a mass moves through spacetime, it may induce entropic variations that do not revert upon returning to the initial position, leaving a "permanent imprint" on the spacetime structure.

This effect can be modeled by introducing an additional term in the gravitational field equations, representing the contribution of irreversible entropic variations to spacetime curvature.

4.5 Integration of LQG, Entropic Gravity, and Entropic Hysteresis

The integration of LQG with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis occurs through the introduction of an entropic field S that interacts with the spin networks of LQG. This interaction connects the discrete quantum properties of spacetime with the emergent thermodynamic principles of Entropic Gravity.

4.5.1 Entropic Field S

The scalar field S represents the accumulation of irreversible entropic variations in spacetime. Its dynamics are described by an effective action that includes terms modeling interactions with spin networks and irreversible entropy variations.

$$\mathcal{S}_S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(-\frac{1}{2} \gamma g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S - \gamma V(S) + \lambda S T \right), \quad (36)$$

where:

- γ is a dimensioned coupling parameter,
- $V(S)$ is the potential of the entropic field S ,
- λ is a coupling constant,

- T is the trace of the matter energy-momentum tensor,
- g is the determinant of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.

4.5.2 Interaction with Spin Networks

The spin networks of LQG, which describe the quantized structure of spacetime, interact with the entropic field S through coupling terms in the effective action. These terms model how variations in the quantum state of spin networks influence the overall entropy of the system.

$$\mathcal{S}_{\text{interaction}} = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(\lambda \hat{S} \cdot \Psi(\Gamma, j_{ab}, i_n) \right), \quad (37)$$

where:

- λ is a coupling parameter,
- $\hat{S}$ is the operator associated with the entropic field S ,
- $\Psi(\Gamma, j_{ab}, i_n)$ is the wavefunction of the spin networks, dependent on the graph Γ , spin quantum numbers j_{ab} , and intertwiner invariants i_n .

4.6 Rationale for Integrating LQG and Entropic Gravity

The primary motivation for unifying LQG with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis lies in the possibility of obtaining a coherent theory that integrates both the discrete quantum structure of spacetime and the emergent thermodynamic phenomena. This unification offers several advantages:

- **Explanation of Gravitational Anomalies:** By integrating LQG with Entropic Gravity, it becomes possible to explain observed gravitational anomalies without relying on dark matter and dark energy. Entropic hysteresis provides an additional mechanism contributing to the gravitational potential on galactic and cosmological scales.
- **Theoretical Consistency:** Combining the spin networks of LQG with the entropic field S ensures a consistent description of quantum and thermodynamic interactions in spacetime, overcoming the limitations of separate theories.
- **Emergence of Quantum Phenomena:** Entropic hysteresis, arising from the quantum properties of spacetime in LQG, allows for the modeling of irreversible and memory effects that influence gravitational dynamics on large scales.

4.7 Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes

An innovative aspect of the unified model is the introduction of quantum crystals of micro black holes. These structures represent discrete quantum configurations of black hole event horizons, where information is preserved thanks to the holographic structure of spacetime.

4.7.1 Information Preservation

The black hole information paradox, proposed by Hawking (5), poses a fundamental challenge to quantum mechanics. According to this paradox, information contained in a mass that forms a black hole would be destroyed during the black hole's evaporation, violating information conservation. Quantum crystals of micro black holes offer a solution to this paradox by preserving information through the discrete structure of spacetime described by LQG. In this view, information is not destroyed but preserved in the quantum configurations of spin networks within the event horizon.

4.7.2 Emergence from LQG

Quantum crystals of micro black holes naturally emerge from the quantized structure of spacetime in LQG. Spin networks, with their quantized nodes and edges, can form stable configurations representing the event horizons of black holes. These discrete configurations allow information to be preserved through quantum transitions that do not destroy the system's overall entropy.

4.7.3 Solution to the Information Paradox

By integrating quantum crystals of micro black holes into the unified model, a mechanism for preserving information in the event horizon is achieved. This occurs through the holographic structure of spin networks, which encode information in a discrete and reversible manner. Thus, even during black hole evaporation, information remains conserved within the quantized network, resolving the paradox proposed by Hawking.

4.7.4 Experimental Evidence

If quantum crystals of micro black holes exist, they could generate characteristic signals in gravitational waves emitted during black hole merger or evaporation processes. The detection of such signals with future gravitational wave missions like *LISA* could provide direct evidence for LQG and support the existence of quantum crystals. Additionally, phenomena such as oscillations in black hole mass

or specific radiation emissions could be observable indicators of these quantum structures.

4.8 Modified Field Equations

The integration of the entropic field S and entropic hysteresis into Einstein's field equations leads to modified equations. The modified Einstein equations are:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} (T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{matter}} + T_{\mu\nu}^S), \quad (38)$$

where $T_{\mu\nu}^S$ is the energy-momentum tensor associated with the entropic field S , defined as:

$$T_{\mu\nu}^S = \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \partial^\alpha S \partial_\alpha S - g_{\mu\nu} V(S). \quad (39)$$

These equations describe how the entropic field contributes to the fabric of spacetime, influencing its geometry and, consequently, gravitational dynamics.

4.9 Numerical Simulations and Modeling

To test the model's validity, it is necessary to develop numerical simulations that incorporate entropic hysteresis and the quantized structure of spacetime provided by LQG. These simulations can be used to study the formation of cosmic structures, the evolution of galactic rotation curves, and the interaction of gravitational waves with quantum crystals of micro black holes.

4.9.1 Formation of Cosmic Structures

Simulations can explore how entropic hysteresis affects the growth of density perturbations on large scales, determining the formation of galaxies and galaxy clusters without the intervention of dark matter. This approach allows for the comparison of the model's predictions with the observed distribution of cosmic structures.

4.9.2 Evolution of Galactic Rotation Curves

By implementing the modified gravitational potential in simulations, it is possible to study the time evolution of galactic rotation curves, verifying whether the model maintains flat velocities without dark matter. This comparison with observational data, such as those in the SPARC catalog, is crucial for validating the model.

4.10 Discussion of Theoretical Implications

The unification of LQG with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis has several theoretical implications:

- **Connection between Quantum Mechanics and Thermodynamics:** The model establishes a direct link between the discrete quantum properties of spacetime and the emergent thermodynamic principles of Entropic Gravity, providing a holistic view of gravity.
- **Solution to the Information Paradox:** The introduction of quantum crystals of micro black holes offers a consistent solution to the information paradox, preserving information within the quantized event horizon structure.
- **Elimination of Dark Components:** The model proposes alternative mechanisms to explain gravitational anomalies without relying on dark matter and dark energy, reducing the need to postulate unseen components.
- **Distinctive Predictions:** Modifications to the field equations and the introduction of entropic hysteresis lead to unique predictions that can be experimentally tested, increasing the model's falsifiability.

4.11 Limitations and Challenges

Despite its potential advantages, the proposed unified model presents several limitations and challenges:

- **Complex Mathematical Formalism:** Integrating LQG with Entropic Gravity and Entropic Hysteresis requires advanced mathematical development, which can be complex and necessitates further research.
- **Determination of Model Parameters:** Precisely determining the introduced parameters, such as the hysteresis parameter γ , poses a significant challenge.
- **Comparison with Observational Data:** It is essential to rigorously compare the model's predictions with a wide range of observational data to verify its validity. This requires interdisciplinary collaborations and access to high-quality data.
- **Compatibility with Established Gravitational Theories:** The model must be verified to ensure it does not contradict the predictions of well-established gravitational theories, such as general relativity, in contexts where

these theories have been precisely confirmed, like gravitational lensing and gravitational waves.

4.12 Role of Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes

The concept of quantum crystals of micro black holes (8) adds an additional dimension to the comparison with other theories.

4.12.1 Information Preservation

The model of quantum crystals could offer a solution to the black hole information paradox by preserving information through the quantum structure of the event horizon. This represents an advantage over other theories that do not directly address this issue.

4.12.2 Experimental Evidence for LQG

If quantum crystals of micro black holes exist, they could produce characteristic signals in gravitational waves or other astrophysical phenomena, providing experimental evidence for LQG and further distinguishing our model from other theories.

4.13 Final Considerations on the Comparison

The unified model proposed offers a new perspective in the quest for a complete gravitational theory that can explain cosmological observations without relying on dark matter and dark energy. While it shares some similarities with other alternative theories, its foundation in LQG and the introduction of entropic hysteresis make it unique.

The comparison with other theories highlights the model's strengths and potential weaknesses. Its ability to provide testable predictions and address fundamental issues like the black hole information paradox makes it an interesting candidate for further studies.

However, significant challenges remain, both theoretically and observationally. It is essential to continue developing the mathematical formalism of the model, compare it with observational data, and communicate the results to the scientific community to foster debate and critical evaluation.

5 Cosmological Implications and Falsifiability of the Unified Model

In this section, we examine the cosmological implications of the unified model that integrates Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), entropic gravity, and spacetime entropic hysteresis. We analyze how the model could explain observed cosmological phenomena, such as the accelerated expansion of the universe and the formation of large-scale structures, without relying on dark matter and dark energy. Additionally, we discuss the model's falsifiability through testable predictions and comparisons with observational data.

5.1 Cosmological Predictions of the Model

The unified model proposes mechanisms that could explain various observed cosmological phenomena:

5.1.1 Accelerated Cosmic Expansion without Dark Energy

Spacetime entropic hysteresis could generate an effective term in the Friedmann equations, contributing to the accelerated expansion of the universe without the need for dark energy. This effect would arise from irreversible entropy variations associated with the quantum structure of spacetime as predicted by LQG.

The modified Friedmann equations could be written as:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} (\rho_{\text{matter}} + \rho_{\text{hysteresis}}) - \frac{kc^2}{a^2}, \quad (40)$$

where $\rho_{\text{hysteresis}}$ represents the energy density associated with entropic hysteresis. This energy density could behave similarly to a dynamic cosmological constant, contributing to the accelerated expansion.

5.1.2 Formation of Large-Scale Structures

The model could influence the formation of cosmic structures by modifying the growth of density perturbations. Entropic hysteresis may alter the gravitational potential on large scales, affecting the rate of growth of perturbations and potentially reproducing the observed distribution of galaxies and clusters without invoking dark matter.

5.1.3 Cosmic Microwave Background Anisotropies

Irreversible entropic variations could leave imprints on the anisotropies of the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB). The model might predict specific modifications to the Integrated Sachs-Wolfe (ISW) effect, which could alter the power spectrum of anisotropies on large angular scales, allowing for comparison with data from satellites like *Planck* (17).

5.1.4 Primordial Gravitational Waves

Quantum fluctuations of spacetime in LQG, amplified by entropic hysteresis, could generate a spectrum of primordial gravitational waves with distinctive characteristics. These gravitational waves might be detectable by future space missions like *LISA*, providing a direct test of the model.

5.2 Comparison with Observational Data

To assess the model's validity, it is essential to compare its predictions with existing cosmological observations.

5.2.1 Galactic Rotation Curves

As previously discussed, the model could explain the flat rotation curves of spiral galaxies through the contribution of entropic hysteresis. Fitting the rotation curves of observed galaxies allows for the estimation of the parameter γ and testing its consistency across different galaxies.

5.2.2 Distribution of Galaxies and Clusters

Numerical simulations incorporating entropic hysteresis can be used to study the formation of large-scale structures. Comparing the simulation results with galaxy and cluster catalogs enables the evaluation of whether the model accurately reproduces the observed distribution of cosmic structures.

5.2.3 CMB Power Spectrum

The model might predict deviations in the CMB power spectrum compared to the standard Λ CDM model. Detailed analyses using cosmological evolution codes like **CAMB** (16) can calculate the anisotropy power spectrum C_ℓ within the hysteresis model and compare it with observational data from *Planck*.

5.2.4 Gravitational Wave Observations

The detection of gravitational waves with specific spectral features predicted by the model could provide strong evidence in its favor. Future missions like *LISA* may detect these primordial gravitational waves, offering a direct test of the unified model.

5.3 Falsifiability of the Model

The ability of a scientific model to make testable predictions that can potentially falsify it is crucial for its validity. The unified model offers several testable predictions that could be used to assess its falsifiability.

5.3.1 Tests through Rotation Curves

If the parameter γ were found to vary significantly across different galaxies or fail to explain flat rotation curves without dark matter, the model could be falsified. Precise measurements of rotation curves across a diverse sample of galaxies are essential for this test.

5.3.2 Analysis of CMB Anisotropies

Significant deviations between the model's predictions and the observed CMB power spectrum could refute the model. A thorough statistical analysis is required to evaluate the compatibility of the model with CMB data.

5.3.3 Detection of Gravitational Waves

The absence of the predicted gravitational wave signals or the observation of a spectrum incompatible with the model's predictions could falsify it. Conversely, the detection of signals consistent with the model would provide strong support.

5.3.4 Laboratory Experiments

Although challenging, high-precision laboratory experiments could seek effects of spacetime quantization on small scales. The failure to observe such effects within the predicted limits could place stringent constraints on the model.

5.4 Observational and Theoretical Challenges

The unified model faces significant challenges both observationally and theoretically.

5.4.1 Complexity of Simulations

Simulations that incorporate entropic hysteresis and the discrete structure of LQG are computationally intensive. Developing efficient and accurate simulation codes poses a significant challenge.

5.4.2 Parameter Ambiguity

Determining the model's parameters, such as γ , requires precise observational data. Degeneracies with other cosmological effects may complicate the interpretation of results.

5.4.3 Consistency with Primordial Nucleosynthesis

The model must be consistent with the primordial nucleosynthesis abundances of light elements. Any deviations could indicate problems with the model's validity.

5.5 Future Directions

To advance the validation and development of the model, the following future directions are proposed:

- **Advanced Theoretical Development:** Further develop the mathematical formalism of the model, integrating LQG with entropic hysteresis and the entropic field S , and deriving precise quantitative predictions.
- **Numerical Simulations:** Implement simulation codes that incorporate entropic hysteresis to study cosmic structure formation, evolution of galactic rotation curves, and interaction of gravitational waves with quantum crystals of micro black holes.
- **Analysis of Existing Observational Data:** Utilize existing astrophysical and cosmological data, such as galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing observations, and CMB measurements, to test the model's predictions and constrain its parameters.
- **Design of New Observations:** Propose and participate in targeted observational campaigns, for example in the field of gravitational waves or precision cosmology, to search for specific signals predicted by the model, such as deviations from standard predictions or effects due to the quantized structure of spacetime.

- **Interdisciplinary Collaborations:** Foster collaborations between theoretical physicists, cosmologists, astrophysicists, and mathematicians to address the multidisciplinary challenges posed by the model, facilitating the integration of diverse expertise.

5.6 Final Considerations on Falsifiability

Science progresses through the formulation of models that can be tested and potentially falsified. The proposed unified model offers specific and verifiable predictions, making it susceptible to the scientific method. Further theoretical studies, simulations, and observations are essential to determine the model's validity and robustness.

* * *

In conclusion, the unified model that integrates LQG with entropic gravity and spacetime entropic hysteresis presents significant cosmological implications and offers a theoretical framework that could explain observations without relying on unseen components like dark matter and dark energy. Its falsifiability through testable predictions makes it an interesting candidate for further investigations in fundamental physics and cosmology.

6 Comparison with Other Theories and Cosmological Models

In this section, we compare the proposed unified model, which integrates Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), entropic gravity, and spacetime entropic hysteresis, with other alternative theories and cosmological models. We discuss the similarities and differences compared to theories such as MOND, TeVeS, $f(R)$ modified gravity theories, string theory, and other modified gravity models. We also evaluate how our model addresses some of the criticisms faced by these alternative theories.

6.1 Comparison with Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND)

Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND) is a theory proposed by Milgrom (13) that modifies Newton's second law for very small accelerations to explain flat galactic rotation curves without invoking dark matter. MOND introduces a fundamental acceleration constant a_0 below which gravitational dynamics are altered.

6.1.1 Similarities with the Unified Model

Our model, through entropic hysteresis, could produce an additional gravitational contribution that becomes significant on galactic scales, similar to MOND. Both models aim to explain gravitational anomalies without introducing dark matter.

6.1.2 Key Differences

While MOND directly modifies the law of gravitation, our model derives gravitational modifications from fundamental principles related to the quantum structure of spacetime and irreversible entropy variations. Additionally, the unified model integrates with LQG, providing a quantum theoretical foundation, whereas MOND remains a phenomenological modification of classical dynamics.

6.2 Comparison with Tensor-Vector-Scalar Theory (TeVeS)

TeVeS, proposed by Bekenstein (14), is a relativistic theory that extends MOND by incorporating tensor, vector, and scalar fields to obtain a theory compatible with general relativity.

6.2.1 Similarities with the Unified Model

Like TeVeS, our model introduces additional fields (the entropic field S) that modify Einstein's field equations. Both theories seek to provide a relativistic framework for explaining gravitational anomalies.

6.2.2 Key Differences

TeVeS introduces ad hoc fields to replicate MOND effects in a relativistic context, while our model derives the entropic field S from quantum spacetime properties in LQG, offering a deeper theoretical justification. This connection provides a more fundamental basis for the introduction of the entropic field compared to the ad hoc nature of TeVeS fields.

6.3 Comparison with $f(R)$ Modified Gravity Theories

$f(R)$ theories modify the Einstein-Hilbert action by replacing the Ricci scalar R with a general function $f(R)$ (18). These theories aim to explain cosmic acceleration and other gravitational phenomena without introducing dark energy or dark matter.

6.3.1 Similarities with the Unified Model

Both $f(R)$ theories and our unified model modify Einstein's field equations to account for cosmological phenomena without dark components. They introduce additional terms that alter gravitational dynamics on large scales.

6.3.2 Key Differences

$f(R)$ theories are purely geometric modifications of the gravitational action, while our model introduces a scalar entropic field derived from quantum and thermodynamic principles. Moreover, the unified model is rooted in the discrete quantum structure of spacetime provided by LQG, offering a quantum foundation absent in $f(R)$ theories.

6.4 Comparison with String Theory

String theory is an attempt to unify all fundamental interactions by describing particles as one-dimensional strings in a multidimensional spacetime.

6.4.1 Similarities with the Unified Model

Both string theory and our unified model seek to unify fundamental forces and incorporate quantum principles into the fabric of spacetime. They both propose fundamental structures (strings or spin networks) that determine spacetime properties at microscopic scales.

6.4.2 Key Differences

String theory requires the existence of extra spatial dimensions and utilizes a continuous spacetime background, whereas LQG-based models consider spacetime to be quantized without the need for additional dimensions. Furthermore, our model incorporates entropic hysteresis and emergent gravity concepts, which are not inherently part of string theory.

6.5 Comparison with Other Modified Gravity Theories

Other modified gravity theories, such as Horndeski's theory (19) and Galileon field theories, introduce scalar fields with non-standard interactions.

6.5.1 Similarities with the Unified Model

These theories often introduce additional fields to explain cosmic acceleration and gravitational anomalies, similar to how our model introduces the entropic field S .

6.5.2 Key Differences

Our model grounds the introduction of the entropic field in the quantum properties of spacetime as described by LQG, providing a more fundamental theoretical basis. In contrast, many modified gravity theories introduce fields in a phenomenological manner without a direct connection to quantum gravity.

6.6 Advantages of the Unified Model over Other Models

The unified model presents several potential advantages over other alternative theories:

- **Solid Theoretical Foundation:** By integrating LQG with entropic gravity, the model is built on a well-developed quantum gravity framework, providing a consistent theoretical basis.
- **Elimination of Unseen Components:** The model proposes mechanisms to explain gravitational anomalies without relying on dark matter and dark energy.
- **Testable Predictions:** The modifications to the field equations and the introduction of entropic hysteresis lead to unique, testable predictions that enhance the model's falsifiability.
- **Response to Existing Criticisms:** The model addresses some criticisms directed at alternative theories, such as the lack of a quantum foundation or the introduction of ad hoc fields.

6.7 Challenges and Criticisms of the Unified Model

Despite its potential strengths, the unified model faces several challenges and criticisms:

- **Complex Mathematical Formalism:** Integrating LQG with entropic hysteresis requires advanced mathematical techniques, which can be complex and necessitate further research.
- **Compatibility with Observations:** The model must be rigorously compared with a wide range of observational data to verify its validity, including galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing, CMB anisotropies, and gravitational wave observations.
- **Distinctive Predictions:** Identifying unique predictions that differentiate the model from other theories is essential for its empirical testing.

- **Acceptance within the Scientific Community:** As with any new theory, the model must undergo rigorous scrutiny and gain acceptance through consistent theoretical development and empirical validation.

6.8 Role of Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes

The concept of quantum crystals of micro black holes (8) adds an additional dimension to the comparison with other theories.

6.8.1 Information Preservation

The quantum crystals model could offer a solution to the black hole information paradox by preserving information through the quantum structure of the event horizon. This represents an advantage over other theories that do not directly address this problem.

6.8.2 Experimental Evidence for LQG

If quantum crystals of micro black holes exist, they could produce characteristic signals in gravitational waves or other astrophysical phenomena, providing experimental evidence for LQG and further distinguishing our model from other theories.

6.9 Final Considerations on the Comparison

The proposed unified model offers a new perspective in the search for a complete gravitational theory that can explain cosmological observations without relying on dark matter and dark energy. While it shares some similarities with other alternative theories, its foundation in LQG and the introduction of entropic hysteresis make it unique.

The comparison with other theories highlights the strengths and potential weaknesses of the model. Its ability to provide testable predictions and address fundamental issues like the black hole information paradox makes it an interesting candidate for further studies.

However, significant challenges remain, both theoretically and observationally. It is essential to continue developing the mathematical formalism of the model, compare it with observational data, and communicate the results to the scientific community to foster debate and critical evaluation.

7 Conclusions and Future Prospects

In this work, we proposed a unified model integrating Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG), entropic gravity, and spacetime entropic hysteresis to explain gravitational and cosmological anomalies without invoking dark matter and dark energy. We explored how entropic hysteresis, derived from the quantum properties of spacetime in LQG, could provide an additional contribution to gravity on astrophysical and cosmological scales.

7.1 Summary of Main Results

The key points of our study are as follows:

- **Theoretical Unification:** We unified LQG with entropic gravity by introducing entropic hysteresis as a mechanism to explain gravitational anomalies on galactic and cosmological scales.
- **Elimination of Dark Matter:** The proposed model could explain galactic rotation curves and other gravitational phenomena without the introduction of dark matter, offering a new interpretation based on entropy variations of spacetime.
- **Cosmic Acceleration without Dark Energy:** Entropic hysteresis could contribute to the accelerated expansion of the universe, eliminating the need for dark energy and providing an alternative explanation based on zero-point energy regulated by LQG.
- **Information Preservation in Black Holes:** The concept of quantum crystals of micro black holes offers a potential solution to the black hole information paradox, preserving information within the event horizon.
- **Testable Predictions:** The model provides specific predictions that could be compared with astrophysical and cosmological observations, making it falsifiable and compliant with the scientific method.

7.2 Implications for Fundamental Physics

The unified model could have significant implications for fundamental physics:

- **New Understanding of Gravity:** Gravity would emerge as an entropic phenomenon derived from the quantum structure of spacetime, offering a new perspective on the nature of gravity and its interactions with matter and energy.

- **Connection between Micro and Macro Cosmos:** By integrating LQG with cosmology, the model connects quantum properties of spacetime with large-scale cosmological phenomena.
- **Possibility of Experimental Verification of LQG:** Through the model's predictions, it might be possible to experimentally test LQG, for instance, by observing gravitational waves with specific characteristics or quantum effects on a cosmological scale.

7.3 Model Limitations

We acknowledge that the proposed model has several limitations and challenges:

- **Incomplete Mathematical Formalism:** The mathematical formalism for fully integrating LQG with entropic hysteresis requires further development, including the quantization of the entropic field and the rigorous derivation of the modified field equations.
- **Need for Comparison with Observational Data:** The model must be thoroughly compared with a wide range of observational data, including galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing, CMB anisotropies, and gravitational waves.
- **Free Parameters:** Determining the precise values of the model's parameters, such as the hysteresis parameter γ , requires robust statistical analyses and high-quality data. It is necessary to establish whether these parameters are universal or vary based on other physical properties.
- **Consistency with Primordial Nucleosynthesis and Other Observations:** The model must be verified to ensure consistency with the abundances of light elements produced during primordial nucleosynthesis and other established cosmological observations.

7.4 Directions for Future Research

To advance the validation and development of the model, we propose the following directions for future research:

- **Advanced Theoretical Development:** Deepen the mathematical formalism of the model, fully integrating LQG with entropic hysteresis and the entropic field S , and deriving precise quantitative predictions.

- **Numerical Simulations:** Implement simulation codes that incorporate entropic hysteresis to study cosmic structure formation, the evolution of galactic rotation curves, and the interaction of gravitational waves with quantum crystals of micro black holes.
- **Analysis of Existing Observational Data:** Utilize existing astrophysical and cosmological data, such as galactic rotation curves, gravitational lensing observations, and CMB measurements, to test the model's predictions and constrain its parameters.
- **Design of New Observations:** Propose and participate in targeted observational campaigns, for example in the field of gravitational waves or precision cosmology, to search for specific signals predicted by the model, such as deviations from standard predictions or effects due to the quantized structure of spacetime.
- **Interdisciplinary Collaborations:** Foster collaborations between theoretical physicists, cosmologists, astrophysicists, and mathematicians to address the multidisciplinary challenges posed by the model, facilitating the integration of diverse expertise.

7.5 Limitations and Challenges of the Model

Despite the potential advantages of the unified model in describing gravitational phenomena without relying on dark matter and dark energy, several limitations and challenges must be addressed.

1. Incomplete Mathematical Formalism

Challenge: Integrating LQG with entropic hysteresis requires a sophisticated mathematical framework. Quantizing the entropic field S within a discrete space-time context is non-trivial and necessitates further development.

Possible Solution: Further investigate the theory using advanced quantization methods in discrete spacetimes, such as spin foam techniques, and develop new mathematical tools to handle scalar fields on spin networks.

2. Determination of Model Parameters

Challenge: Parameters introduced in the model, such as the hysteresis parameter γ , need precise determination for quantitative predictions. Without accurate values, the model remains qualitative.

Possible Solution: Utilize existing observational data, such as galactic rotation curves and cosmological observations, to constrain the model's parameters through detailed statistical analyses.

3. Compatibility with Cosmological Observations

Challenge: The model must be consistent with a wide range of observations, including the abundances of light elements produced during primordial nucleosynthesis, CMB anisotropies, and large-scale structure formation.

Possible Solution: Conduct detailed numerical simulations that incorporate entropic hysteresis and compare the outcomes with observational data. This includes analyzing structure formation and ensuring that nucleosynthesis predictions remain unaffected.

4. Effects on Different Scales

Challenge: It is necessary to verify that the model does not introduce undesirable effects on smaller scales, such as within the Solar System, where general relativity has been confirmed with high precision.

Possible Solution: Analyze the model's predictions in weak-field and low-entropy regimes to ensure that it reduces to general relativity on small scales and in conditions where entropy variations are negligible.

5. Distinctive Predictions

Challenge: Without unique predictions, it is difficult to distinguish the model from other theories.

Possible Solution: Identify specific phenomena or signatures predicted by the model, such as unique features in gravitational wave spectra or specific modifications to lensing patterns, that can be tested observationally.

6. Acceptance within the Scientific Community

Challenge: As with all new theories, the model must undergo rigorous scrutiny and convince the scientific community of its validity.

Possible Solution: Publish detailed theoretical developments and empirical analyses in peer-reviewed journals, present findings at scientific conferences, and engage with the broader scientific community to receive constructive feedback and foster acceptance.

Prospects for Overcoming the Limitations

To address these challenges, we propose the following actions:

- **Interdisciplinary Research:** Collaborate with experts in quantum gravity, cosmology, astrophysics, and mathematics to develop the theoretical framework and perform comprehensive analyses.
- **Advanced Numerical Simulations:** Develop and utilize high-performance computing simulations that incorporate entropic hysteresis and quantum spacetime structures to explore the model's implications in detail.
- **Targeted Observational Studies:** Design observational studies aimed at detecting the specific predictions of the model, such as unique gravitational wave signatures or modifications in gravitational lensing.

- **Publications and Dissemination:** Share research findings through scientific publications, conference presentations, and seminars to engage with the scientific community and encourage collaborative efforts.

7.6 Final Considerations

The unified model presented represents an ambitious attempt to address some of the most fundamental open questions in modern physics. While significant progress has been made, further theoretical and empirical work is necessary to overcome existing challenges and fully validate the model's predictions.

The possibility of explaining gravitational anomalies without invoking dark matter and dark energy could have a profound impact on our understanding of the universe. Additionally, the model opens new avenues for testing Loop Quantum Gravity through empirical observations, bridging the gap between quantum gravity theories and cosmological phenomena.

We encourage continued research and discussion on the model, aiming to deepen our understanding and experimentally verify its predictions. Science advances through the critical examination of ideas and rigorous testing of theories, and we hope that this work contributes to stimulating new research and discoveries in the fields of fundamental physics and cosmology.

A Detailed Model and Its Implications

In this appendix, we provide a detailed exploration of the proposed unified model, integrating Loop Quantum Gravity (LQG) with Entropic Gravity and Spacetime Entropic Hysteresis. We examine the theoretical and observational implications of the model, offering comprehensive mathematical derivations and direct connections to the main sections of the document.

A.1 Connections with the Main Sections

The unified model described in Sections 2 and 4 is further elaborated in this appendix. Specifically, we refer to **Section 3** for the definition of entropic hysteresis and to **Section 4** for the integration with LQG.

A.2 Complete Mathematical Derivations

Here we present the complete mathematical derivations supporting the claims made in the main sections. Each step is detailed to ensure clarity and transparency of the model.

A.2.1 Derivation of the Equation of Motion for the Entropic Field

Consider the effective action of the entropic field S introduced in **Section 4**:

$$S_S = \int d^4x \sqrt{-g} \left(-\frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S - V(S) - JS \right). \quad (41)$$

Varying the action S_S with respect to the field S , we obtain the equation of motion:

$$\square S = \frac{dV}{dS} + J, \quad (42)$$

where $\square = g^{\mu\nu} \nabla_\mu \nabla_\nu$ is the d'Alembertian operator in curved spacetime.

A.2.2 Derivation of the Energy-Momentum Tensor

The energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}^S$ associated with the entropic field S is obtained by varying the action with respect to the metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$:

$$T_{\mu\nu}^S = \partial_\mu S \partial_\nu S - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \partial^\alpha S \partial_\alpha S - g_{\mu\nu} V(S). \quad (43)$$

This tensor contributes to the modified Einstein equations presented in **Section 4**:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} (T_{\mu\nu}^{\text{matter}} + T_{\mu\nu}^S), \quad (44)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor and Λ is the cosmological constant.

A.3 Examples of Model Application

We present concrete examples of how the unified model can explain observed phenomena.

A.3.1 Galactic Rotation Curves

As described in **Section 3**, the rotation curves of spiral galaxies can be explained by the modified gravitational potential including entropic hysteresis:

$$\Phi_{\text{gravitational}}(r) = \Phi_{\text{Newtonian}}(r) + \gamma \ln \left(\frac{r}{r_0} \right), \quad (45)$$

where γ is the entropic hysteresis parameter and r_0 is a reference radius. This additional term allows maintaining constant rotation velocities without dark matter.

A.3.2 Gravitational Lensing

Gravitational lensing, as discussed in **Section 4**, shows light deflection that cannot be explained solely by visible mass. The introduction of entropic hysteresis modifies the deflection angle:

$$\alpha = \alpha_{\text{Newtonian}} + \alpha_{\text{hysteresis}}, \quad (46)$$

where $\alpha_{\text{hysteresis}}$ depends on the modified potential and can be calculated by integrating along the light path.

A.3.3 CMB Anisotropies

The entropic hysteresis model may leave imprints on the CMB anisotropies, particularly affecting the Integrated Sachs-Wolfe (ISW) effect. By modifying the gravitational potential over time, the model can influence the CMB power spectrum, allowing for comparison with observational data.

A.4 Conclusion of Appendix A

This appendix provided a detailed exploration of the unified model, integrating Loop Quantum Gravity with Entropic Gravity and entropic hysteresis. We presented complete mathematical derivations and examples of model applications, reinforcing the theoretical consistency and empirical relevance of the proposed framework.

B Mathematical Details of Entropic Gravity

In this appendix, we provide an in-depth treatment of the mathematical aspects of Entropic Gravity as proposed by Verlinde (1). We examine the fundamental derivations that connect entropy, temperature, energy, and gravitational force, and how these emergent concepts integrate with the unified model described in the main sections (**Sections 2 and 4**).

B.1 Derivation of Gravitational Force as Entropic Force

This subsection expands the derivation of gravitational force as an entropic force, providing intermediate steps and additional mathematical details.

B.1.1 Entropy Variation

Consider a mass m placed at a displacement Δx from a holographic surface. As the mass approaches the surface, the associated entropy variation ΔS changes. According to Verlinde, the entropy variation is proportional to the displacement Δx :

$$\Delta S = 2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \Delta x, \quad (47)$$

where k_B is Boltzmann's constant, c is the speed of light, and $\hbar$ is the reduced Planck constant.

B.1.2 Unruh Temperature

According to the Unruh effect, an accelerated observer perceives the vacuum as a thermal bath of particles with temperature T :

$$T = \frac{\hbar a}{2\pi k_B c}, \quad (48)$$

which is proportional to the acceleration a .

B.1.3 Entropic Force

The entropic force F is defined by the thermodynamic relation:

$$F = T \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta x}. \quad (49)$$

Substituting the temperature T from Equation (48) and the entropy variation ΔS from Equation (47), we obtain:

$$F = \left(\frac{\hbar a}{2\pi k_B c} \right) \left(2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \right) \quad (50)$$

$$= ma. \quad (51)$$

This is Newton's second law, $F = ma$, suggesting that the gravitational force can be interpreted as an emergent entropic force.

B.2 Derivation of Newton's Universal Law of Gravitation

To derive Newton's universal law of gravitation from Entropic Gravity, consider a mass M surrounded by a spherical surface of radius r (the holographic screen). The number of degrees of freedom (bits) on the surface is proportional to its area:

$$N = \frac{A}{\ell_P^2} = \frac{4\pi r^2}{\ell_P^2}, \quad (52)$$

where ℓ_P is the Planck length, defined as:

$$\ell_P = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}}. \quad (53)$$

B.2.1 Equipartition Relation

Assume that the total energy associated with the N bits is given by the equipartition relation:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} N k_B T. \quad (54)$$

Substituting the energy $E = Mc^2$, we obtain:

$$Mc^2 = \frac{1}{2} N k_B T. \quad (55)$$

Solving for the temperature T :

$$T = \frac{2Mc^2}{Nk_B}. \quad (56)$$

Substituting N from Equation (52):

$$T = \frac{2Mc^2}{\frac{4\pi r^2}{\ell_P^2} k_B} \quad (57)$$

$$= \frac{Mc^2 \ell_P^2}{2\pi r^2 k_B}. \quad (58)$$

B.2.2 Calculation of Gravitational Force

Using the relation for entropic force $F = ma$ and substituting T from Equation (56), we obtain:

$$F = T \frac{\Delta S}{\Delta x} \quad (59)$$

$$= \left(\frac{Mc^2 \ell_P^2}{2\pi r^2 k_B} \right) \left(2\pi k_B \frac{mc}{\hbar} \right) \quad (60)$$

$$= \frac{Mmc^3 \ell_P^2}{r^2 \hbar}. \quad (61)$$

Using the definition of the Planck length $\ell_P = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}}$:

$$F = \frac{Mmc^3 \left(\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}\right)}{r^2 \hbar} \quad (62)$$

$$= \frac{GMm}{r^2}. \quad (63)$$

This is Newton's universal law of gravitation, $F = \frac{GMm}{r^2}$, derived from Entropic Gravity. This demonstrates how gravitational laws can emerge from thermodynamic and informational principles without postulating gravity as a fundamental force.

B.3 Implications of Entropic Gravity

The derivation of gravitational laws from Entropic Gravity has profound implications for our understanding of the nature of gravity and spacetime:

- **Gravity as an Emergent Phenomenon:** Entropic Gravity suggests that gravity is not a fundamental force but emerges from the thermodynamic properties of the universe. This approach could facilitate the unification of gravity with other fundamental forces, which are already described in terms of fundamental interactions.

- **Connection with Quantum Mechanics:** By integrating thermodynamic and quantum concepts, Entropic Gravity offers a pathway to connect general relativity with quantum mechanics, potentially paving the way for a quantum theory of gravity.
- **Interpretation of Dark Energy and Dark Matter:** Since Entropic Gravity provides an alternative explanation for gravitational laws, it could also offer new insights into cosmological phenomena such as dark energy and dark matter, suggesting that these phenomena might be reinterpreted as emergent effects of entropic gravity.
- **Thermodynamic Equilibrium Principle:** The idea that gravitational laws derive from thermodynamic principles implies that spacetime could be considered a thermodynamic system in equilibrium or evolving toward equilibrium, opening new perspectives on cosmological dynamics.

B.4 Criticisms and Limitations of Entropic Gravity

Despite its intriguing implications, Entropic Gravity has faced several criticisms and presents some limitations:

- **Non-Universal Modifications:** Some studies have shown that the gravitational modifications arising from Entropic Gravity may not be universal, varying depending on the specific conditions of the system, which could complicate the explanation of cosmological phenomena on large scales.
- **Fundamental Assumptions:** The derivation of gravitational laws relies on certain fundamental assumptions, such as the proportionality of entropy variation to mass displacement. These assumptions require further justification or derivation from deeper principles.
- **Compatibility with General Relativity:** It is necessary to demonstrate how Entropic Gravity fully integrates with Einstein's general relativity, especially in contexts where general relativity's predictions are highly accurate, such as in gravitational lensing and gravitational waves.
- **Distinctive Predictions:** To distinguish Entropic Gravity from traditional gravitational theories, it is essential to identify unique predictions that can be experimentally tested. So far, some predictions remain theoretical and require observational verification.

B.5 Conclusions on the Fundamentals of Entropic Gravity

Entropic Gravity offers an interesting perspective on the emergent nature of gravity, linking thermodynamic and informational principles with gravitational laws. Although this theory presents promising implications for fundamental physics and cosmology, it requires further theoretical developments and experimental verifications to overcome the currently identified criticisms and limitations. The subsequent section will delve deeper into how the introduction of entropic hysteresis can enhance Entropic Gravity, integrating it with Loop Quantum Gravity to more comprehensively address observed gravitational anomalies.

C Bibliography

References

- [1] Verlinde, E. (2011). On the Origin of Gravity and the Laws of Newton. *Journal of High Energy Physics*, **2011**(4), 29.
- [2] 't Hooft, G. (1993). Dimensional reduction in quantum gravity. *arXiv preprint gr-qc/9310026*.
- [3] Susskind, L. (1995). The World as a Hologram. *Journal of Mathematical Physics*, **36**(11), 6377–6396.
- [4] Unruh, W. G. (1976). Notes on Black Hole Evaporation. *Physical Review D*, **14**(4), 870–892.
- [5] Hawking, S. W. (1975). Particle Creation by Black Holes. *Communications in Mathematical Physics*, **43**(3), 199–220.
- [6] Rovelli, C. (2004). *Quantum Gravity*. Cambridge University Press.
- [7] Thiemann, T. (2007). *Modern Canonical Quantum General Relativity*. Cambridge University Press.
- [8] Cambi, P. (2024). Quantum Crystals of Micro Black Holes: A Novel Hypothesis. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14056570>
- [9] Rubin, V. C., Ford, W. K., & Thonnard, N. (1980). Rotational properties of 21 SC galaxies with a large range of luminosities and radii. *The Astrophysical Journal*, **238**, 471–487.
- [10] Perlmutter, S., et al. (1999). Measurements of Omega and Lambda from 42 High-Redshift Supernovae. *The Astrophysical Journal*, **517**(2), 565–586.
- [11] Riess, A. G., et al. (1998). Observational Evidence from Supernovae for an Accelerating Universe and a Cosmological Constant. *The Astronomical Journal*, **116**(3), 1009–1038.
- [12] Bertone, G., & Tait, T. M. P. (2018). A new era in the search for dark matter. *Nature*, **562**(7725), 51–56.
- [13] Milgrom, M. (1983). A Modification of the Newtonian Dynamics as a Possible Alternative to the Hidden Mass Hypothesis. *The Astrophysical Journal*, **270**, 365–370.

- [14] Bekenstein, J. D. (2004). Relativistic Gravitation Theory for the Modified Newtonian Dynamics Paradigm. *Physical Review D*, **70**(8), 083509.
- [15] Lelli, F., McGaugh, S. S., & Schombert, J. M. (2016). SPARC: Mass Models for 175 Disk Galaxies with Spitzer Photometry and Accurate Rotation Curves. *The Astronomical Journal*, **152**(6), 157.
- [16] Lewis, A., Challinor, A., & Lasenby, A. (2000). Efficient Computation of Cosmic Microwave Background Anisotropies in Closed Friedmann-Robertson-Walker Models. *The Astrophysical Journal*, **538**(2), 473–476.
- [17] Planck Collaboration. (2018). Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, **641**, A6.
- [18] Sotiriou, T. P., & Faraoni, V. (2010). $f(R)$ Theories of Gravity. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, **82**(1), 451–497.
- [19] Horndeski, G. W. (1974). Second-order scalar-tensor field equations in a four-dimensional space. *International Journal of Theoretical Physics*, **10**(6), 363–384.
- [20] Connes, A. (1994). *Noncommutative Geometry*. Academic Press.
- [21] Madore, J. (1999). *An Introduction to Noncommutative Differential Geometry and its Physical Applications*. Cambridge University Press.
- [22] Ashtekar, A. (1986). New variables for classical and quantum gravity. *Physical Review Letters*, **57**(18), 2244.
- [23] Barbero, J. F. (1995). Real Ashtekar variables for Lorentzian signature spacetimes. *Physical Review D*, **51**(10), 5507.
- [24] Perez, A. (2003). Spin foam models for quantum gravity. *Classical and Quantum Gravity*, **20**(6), R43.
- [25] Easson, D. A., Frampton, P. H., & Smoot, G. F. (2011). Entropic accelerating universe. *Physics Letters B*, **696**(3), 273–277.
- [26] Maldacena, J. M. (1998). The Large N Limit of Superconformal Field Theories and Supergravity. *Advances in Theoretical and Mathematical Physics*, **2**(2), 231–252.